

Preparation and physico-chemical properties of new dimeric $[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{M}_2(\text{sb})_2 \cdot x\text{THF}]$ and monomeric $[\text{M}(\text{sb})_2 \cdot x\text{THF}]$ ($\text{M} = \text{Co}^{\text{II}}, \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$) complexes containing salicylidene-sulphadiazine ligand

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Abstract : Reactions of anhydrous MCl_2 with sodium salt of salicylidene-sulphadiazine in (1 : 1 and 1 : 2) molar ratios afforded complexes of the types $[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{M}_2(\text{sb})_2 \cdot x\text{THF}]$ (1, 3; dimeric) and $[\text{M}(\text{sb})_2 \cdot x\text{THF}]$ (2, 4; monomeric) in THF-MeOH solution [where $\text{M} = \text{Co}^{\text{II}}$ and Ni^{II} , sb = salicylidene-sulphadiazine (ssdH); $X = 4$ for 1, 3 and 2 for 2, 4]. These coloured solid and soluble (THF, methanol, ethanol, DMF and DMSO) complexes have been characterized by elemental (M, C, H, N, S and Cl), TGA, analysis and spectral (IR, UV-Visible and FAB-MS) as well as magnetic studies. On the basis of these spectral analyses distorted octahedral geometry around central metal atom have been proposed tentatively.

Keywords : Cobalt(II), nickel(II), salicylidene-sulphadiazine complex, FAB-MS, IR, electronic, magnetic studies.

Introduction

During the last decade sulphadruugs have attracted considerable attention due to their wide range of biological and industrial applications¹⁻⁵. Some sulphadruugs have been also used in treatment of tuberculosis, leprosy, malarial, cancer and removal of various infections from humans and animal system⁶. Some metallic sulphadruug complexes showed enhanced pharmacological and toxicological activities⁷. Furthermore, some metal chelates of sulphadruugs showed more bacteriostatic activity⁸ than the drugs. Sulphadruugs are considered to be important class of chelating ligands for the synthesis and structural point of view⁹⁻¹². Additionally our earlier findings on alkoxide¹³⁻¹⁶, benzoxazole/benzimidazole and Schiff base, mixed ligand complexes of these transition metals¹⁷⁻¹⁹ have also shown variation in their coordination number. Keeping above facts in view and results obtained recently by the reaction of early lanthanide and sulphadruug²⁰ prompted us to synthesize sulphadruug complexes of transition metal (Ni^{II} and Co^{II}) and characterize them using various spectroscopic techniques such as IR, UV-Visible, TGA, and FAB-MS as well as magnetic studies.

Results and discussion

The new complexes of cobalt(II) and nickel(II) have been synthesized by the reaction of anhydrous MCl_2 with sodium salts of salicylidene-sulphadiazine in THF-MeOH solution, which can be represented by the following chemical equations :

[where, $\text{M} = \text{Co}^{\text{II}}, \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$; sb = Schiff base, salicylidene-sulphadiazine (ssdH)].

All these complexes are light coloured solids and soluble in polar solvents like THF, DMF and DMSO etc. The synthetic and analytical details are given in experi-

mental section, under the headings synthesis of complexes.

Electronic spectra :

Electronic spectra of nickel(II) complexes have been measured in DMF/DMSO, which exhibits two types of bands, *d-d* transition bands and charge transfer bands. The observed electronic absorption in the range 25974–27174 cm^{-1} , correspond to ${}^3A_{2g} \xrightarrow{\nu_3} {}^3T_{1g} (P)$, which is characteristic for the octahedral geometry¹⁵ around nickel(II). The bands observed in the range of 28489–29940 cm^{-1} may be attributed to the charge-transfer transitions from the phenolate moieties to central metal nickel(II). Whereas, electronic spectra of cobalt(II) complexes exhibits a multiple band (asymmetric) in the region $18080 \pm 90 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which may be assigned to ${}^4T_{1g} (F) \xrightarrow{\nu_3} {}^4T_{1g} (P)$ transition; appearance of a shoulder on the higher frequency side in the region $19625 \pm 220 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be assigned to spin forbidden transitions and to doublet states derived from the free ion 2G and 2H terms, which are characteristic of octahedral geometry¹³. The ${}^4A_{2g} (F) \xrightarrow{\nu_2} {}^4T_{1g} (F)$ transition is not normally observed, being formally a two electron transition. On the basis of above observations, an octahedral structure may be proved.

Infrared spectra :

Important IR data are listed in Table 1. Salient features of IR spectra of metal complexes are : disappearance²¹ of broad band at 3423 cm^{-1} due to the deprotonation of phenolic OH and shifting of ν_{C-O} towards higher frequency $\nu 48 \pm 4 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ scale compared to the salicylidene-sulphadiazine may be due to the formation of metal-oxygen bond, further supported by appearance of new band²² in the region 569–560 cm^{-1} due to the ν_{M-O} . The ligand²⁰ *ssdH* show strong band at 1650 cm^{-1} due to $\nu_{C=N}$, which get considerably shifted lower side and appear in the region $1606\text{--}1588 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, such lower shifting of $\nu_{C=N}$ com-

pare to the *ssdH* and appearance of new band in region $435\text{--}400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be due to the $\nu_{M\leftarrow N}$ bond formation²³. The NH band appear in complexes in the region $3257 \pm 3 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ compared to the parent ligand 3255 cm^{-1} indicating non-involvement²⁴ of NH group in the complex formation. In the complexes containing THF molecules, asymmetric and symmetric C-O-C stretching frequencies were observed at $\nu 896, 907$ and 884 cm^{-1} and $753, 777$ and 766 cm^{-1} , respectively compare to $\nu 1020\text{--}1015 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (THF asymmetric) and $860\text{--}850 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (THF symmetric) in uncoordinated THF molecule. Such shifting of asymmetric and symmetric stretching of C-O-C to frequency to lower side in the complexes suggests coordination of THF molecule by oxygen to metal²⁵. Nickel(II) and cobalt(II) form six coordinated complexes where the chlorine forms bridges between two metal center $[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2M_2]$. This is further supported by FAB-MS spectral studies showing dimeric nature of the complexes **1** and **3**. A intense band at $\nu 320\text{--}269 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ has been assigned for ν_{Co-Cl} characteristic of bridging¹⁴ chloride. In chloro complexes of nickel ν_{Ni-Cl} for bridging¹⁶ chloride occurred at $280\text{--}248 \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Magnetic moment :

Cobalt(II) ($3d^7$) high spin complexes, the magnetic moment values (μ_{eff}) are expected to be 3.90 B.M., whereas actual values generally observed in the range 4.4–5.2 B.M. due to orbital contributions²⁶ and vary with stereochemistry ranges, 4.4–4.8 for tetrahedral (T_d), 4.8–5.4 for trigonalbipyramidal (TBP) and 4.7–5.2 B.M. for octahedral (O_h) of the complexes. Synthesized complexes gave (μ_{eff}) values 5.2 ± 2 B.M. correspond to O_h geometry^{26a}. Similarly nickel(II) complexes gave room temperature magnetic moments ($\nu 3.20$ B.M.) which are in agreement with octahedral geometry^{26b}.

Table 1. IR spectral data (cm^{-1}) of the salicylidene-sulphadiazine and their metal complexes

Sl. No.	Complex	ν_{O-H}	ν_{N-H}	$\nu_{C=N}$ azomethine	ν_{C-O} phenolic	ν_{C-O-C} THF (asymmetric)	ν_{C-O-C} THF (symmetric)	ν_{M-O}	$\nu_{M\leftarrow N}$	ν_{M-Cl-M}
1.	<i>ssdH</i>	3423	3255	1650	1394					
2.	$[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2Co_2(ssd)_2 \cdot 4THF]$ 1		3258	1588	1440	888, 894, 903	755, 766, 773	569	435	320
3.	$[Co(ssd)_2 \cdot 2THF]$ 2		3256	1587	1441	886, 897, 907	751, 769, 778	569	430	269
4.	$[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2Ni_2(ssd)_2 \cdot 4THF]$ 3		3252	1586	1493	883, 896, 909	759, 763, 779	567	428	280
5.	$[Ni(ssd)_2 \cdot 2THF]$ 4		3254	1606	1490	882, 899, 910	750, 767, 779	560	400	248

Thermogravimetric analysis :

Non-horizontal thermogravimetric²⁸ curve of the complex $[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Co}_2(\text{ssd})_2 \cdot 4\text{THF}]$ **1** and $[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Ni}_2(\text{ssd})_2 \cdot 4\text{THF}]$ **3** has been carried out from 33 °C to 985 °C temperature. Cobalt(II) complex $[(\text{Cl})_2\text{Co}_2(\text{ssd})_2 \cdot 4\text{THF}]$ **1** shows three step degradation. Molecular mass of complex is 1182.18. First degradation appeared at 164.62 °C temperature followed by second degradation at 417.18 °C temperature due to organic pyrolysis. Cobalt oxide residue formed at 985 °C temperature in last step. The residue of cobalt(II) complex is 8.40% which is equal to approximate mass of the complex 75 (8.36%).

Similarly, molecular mass of complex $[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Ni}_2(\text{ssd})_2 \cdot 4\text{THF}]$ **3** is 1180.18. Nickel(II) complex shows two step decomposition. First decomposition occurs at 215 °C temperature due to formation of monomer which is equal to approximate mass of the complex 441.24 (37.38%). Second degradation appeared at 985 °C due to elimination of organic moiety leaving to nickel oxide as residue, which is also confirmed by remaining material percentage 8.37 (8.35).

FAB-mass spectra :

FAB-MS spectra and the fragmentation²⁸⁻³⁰ patterns of complexes **1**, **4** represented in (Figs. 1-2) and (Schemes 1-2) respectively. The mass spectrum of the complex $[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Co}_2(\text{ssd})_2 \cdot 4\text{THF}]$ **1** showed molecular ion peak at m/z 1184 $[(\text{C}_{50}\text{H}_{58}\text{Cl}_2\text{Co}_2\text{N}_8\text{O}_{10}\text{S}_2)$; Calcd. mass = 1184], supports the molecular composition and dimeric nature of the complex **1**. Several peaks were also observed in mass spectrum at m/z 1113, 965, 897, 832, 789, 773, 700, 617, 593, 523, 480, 449, 408, 355, 343, 251, 156 and 94 due to formation of various radicals in complex **1**. The mass spectrum of the complex $[\text{Ni}(\text{ssd})_2 \cdot 2\text{THF}]$ **4** showed molecular ion peak at m/z 913 $[(\text{C}_{42}\text{H}_{42}\text{NiN}_8\text{O}_8\text{S}_2)$; Calcd. 910], which supports the molecular mass and monomeric nature of the complex. Several peaks were also observed in mass spectrum at m/z 839, 767, 697, 665, 663, 593, 493, 427, 413, 343, 251, 224, 156 and 71 and monomer m/z 413 due to successive fragmentation of complex **3**.

Experimental

Materials and measurement :

Reagent grade (BDH) precursors to ligands were used. Solvents were purified by the standard procedures. Nickel(II) and cobalt(II) chloride was purchased from E. Merck and used after making them anhydrous by heating over HCl gas atmosphere^{13,14}. All others chemicals were purchased from commercial sources and used as such. Chloride was estimated by Volhard's method³¹.

Elemental analyses for C, H and N were performed on a Heraceous Carlo Erba 1108 elemental analyser. Metal content was determined in laboratory by the reported methods³¹. Sulphur was estimated as BaSO_4 gravimetrically. The electronic spectra of the compounds were recorded in DMF using 10 mm quartz cell on a Perkin-Elmer Lambda 15 UV-Vis spectrophotometer. The infra-red spectra of ligands and their complexes were recorded in KBr pellets on a Perkin-Elmer 1000 FT-IR spectrophotometer in the range 4000–200 cm^{-1} . Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was carried on Mettler Toledo with heating rate 10 °C min^{-1} . The FAB-MS spectra were recorded on JEOL SX 102/DA-6000 mass spectrometer/data system using argon/xenon (6 kV, 10 mA) as the FAB-gas. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made on Gouy balance.

Synthesis of Schiff base :

The salicylidene-sulphadiazine was synthesized according to the procedure described in publication²⁹.

Synthesis of complexes :

$[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Co}_2(\text{ssd})_2 \cdot 4\text{THF}]$ (**1**) : A methanolic solution of Na(ssd) (1.035 g, 4.43 mmol) was added dropwise with constant stirring to cobalt(II)chloride (1.204 g, 4.43 mmol) (THF ~ 20 ml). The reaction mixture was allowed to reflux for ~ 4 h. The separated NaCl was removed by filtration and filtrate was concentrated after removing the excess of solvent by distillation. The product was dried under reduced pressure, which was purified by recrystallization from THF-MeOH mixture (purity was further checked by TLC) to afford brown crystalline solid. Yield :

Fig. 1. FAB-MS spectra of $[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Co}_2(\text{ssd})_2 \cdot 4\text{THF}] \mathbf{1}$.

88%, m.p. 240 °C (Found : C, 50.02; H, 4.91; N, 9.41; S, 5.46; Cl, 5.29; Co, 9.93. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{50}\text{H}_{58}\text{Cl}_2\text{N}_8\text{Co}_2\text{O}_{10}\text{S}_2$: C, 50.72; H, 4.49; N, 9.46; S, 5.42; Cl, 9.96; Co, 9.92%).

$[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Ni}_2(\text{ssd})_2 \cdot 4\text{THF}] \mathbf{(3)}$: Similar procedure was adopted for synthesis of complex **(3)** by interaction of

nickel(II) chloride and sodium salts of Schiff base in 1 : 1 molar ratio(s). Yellow colour, yield : 78% , m.p. 245 d °C (Found : C, 50.11 ; H, 4.39; N, 9.25; S, 4.99; Cl, 5.23; Ni, 9.01. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{50}\text{H}_{58}\text{Cl}_2\text{N}_8\text{Ni}_2\text{O}_{10}\text{S}_2$: C, 50.74 ; H, 4.94; N, 9.47; S, 5.42; Cl, 5.99; Ni, 9.92%).

Fig. 2. FAB-MS spectra of $[\text{Ni}_2(\text{ssd})_2 \cdot 2\text{THF}]$ **4**.

$[\text{Co}(\text{ssd})_2 \cdot 2\text{THF}]$ (**2**) : The bis complexes $[\text{Co}(\text{ssd})_2 \cdot 2\text{THF}]$ have also been prepared by adopting the similar procedure as described for monochloro complex by interaction of metal(II) chloride and sodium salts of Schiff bases in 1 : 2 molar ratio(s). Brownish yellow

colour, yield : 61%, m.p. 255 °C (Found : C, 55.40; H, 4.60; N, 12.03; S, 6.87; Co, 6.41. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{42}\text{H}_{42}\text{N}_8\text{CoO}_8\text{S}_2$: C, 55.44 ; H, 4.65; N, 12.32; S, 7.05; Co, 6.48%).

$[\text{Ni}(\text{ssd})_2 \cdot 2\text{THF}]$ (**4**) : The bis complexes

Scheme 1. Mass fragmentation pattern of complex $[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Co}_2(\text{ssd})_2 \cdot 4\text{THF}]$ 1.

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Scheme 2. Fragmentation pattern of complex cobalt $[\text{Ni}_2(\text{ssd})_2 \cdot 2\text{THF}]$ 4.

$[\text{Ni}(\text{ssd})_2 \cdot 2\text{THF}]$ have also been prepared by adopting the similar procedure as described for monochloro complex by interaction of metal(II) chloride and sodium salts of Schiff bases in 1 : 2 molar ratio(s). Brownish yellow colour, yield : 92%, m.p. 255 °C (Found : C, 55.10; H, 4.01; N, 12.01; S, 6.89; Ni, 6.16. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{42}\text{H}_{42}\text{N}_8\text{NiO}_8\text{S}_2$: C, 55.46; H, 4.65; N, 12.32; S, 7.05; Ni, 6.45%).

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